

How to pick a data repository

General: Where to start?

- 1) Established repositories in the relevant scientific communities
- 2) Repositories from (or recommended by) the respective Institution
- 3) Funding organisations' demands or recommendations
- 4) Interdisciplinary repositories
- 5) Other repositories that fulfill relevant criteria

How accessible will your data be for others?

Does the repository provide [Open Access](#)?

Is your data issued under a [Creative Commons](#), or similar, licence?

Criteria

Infrastructure:

- Policy
- Terms of use
- Long-term sustainability
- Follows community standards (e.g. [FAIR](#), [TRUST](#))
- Reputation

Usage:

- Cost, fee
- Size
- Upload restrictions
- Persistent identifier service (e.g. DOI)
- Metadata inclusion

Certificates to look out for

[CoreTrustSeal](#) [Nestor Seal \(DIN31644\)](#) [ISO16363](#)

Where to find?

re3data.org

[re3data](https://re3data.org)

Authors: Lynn Schneider (ORCID: 0009-0001-5756-7935) and Justine Vandendorpe (ORCID: 0000-0002-9421-8582)
Institution: ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences (ROR ID: <https://ror.org/0259fwx54>)
Date of publication: 2024-09-02

